

A STUDY ON THE CORRELATION BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND ORGANIZATIONAL CYNICISM PERCEIVED BY VOCATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Objective of this study is to reveal the level of perceived organizational justice and perceived organizational cynicism of vocational high school teachers and whether or not a correlation exists between perceived organizational justice and perceived organizational cynicism. The study has been performed in compliance with the review model. It was actualized with 286 teachers selected by random sampling from vocational high schools and technical Anatolian high schools in Bağcılar district of Istanbul in the academic years 2016-2017. In the study, "Organizational Justice Scale" and "Organizational Cynicism Scale" have been utilized in order to determine perceived organizational justice and perceived organizational cynicism, respectively, as data collection tool. In analyzing data thus collected, SPSS packaged software have been used, and arithmetic mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation analysis have been made based on the data. According to data analysis results, it has been observed that overall perceived organizational justice and perceived organizational cynicism of vocational high school teachers is "moderate". A negative "high" level of significant correlations has been found between perceived organizational justice and perceived lower perceived organizational cynicism of vocational high school teachers.

Keywords: teacher, organizational justice, organizational cynicism

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1. Introduction

Organization can be defined as the formations formed by minimum two people to achieve a collective goal or a series of collective goals, regulating the efforts of a group of people for achieving certain goals (Genç, 2007), comprising of people and technologies, regulating people's relations with each other or with their businesses (Balci, 2002), being pre-planned by people involving task distribution and assignments, where they work in coordination (Öztekin, 2002). It is not possible for organizations to function properly without human factor. Employees constitute a whole in an organization and find a common ground so that organization can perform all its functions. One of the primary conditions for organizations to achieve job satisfaction for people on a common ground in the work environment is to secure organizational justice. The organizational justice, which is defined as employee's opinion on to what extent the administrative practices in the organization are fair (Eskew, 1993; Greenberg, 1990; Greenberg and Colquitt, 2005; Moorman, 1991), is addressed in three dimensions in the literature: distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice. Distributive justice is grounded on the fairness of the outcomes of the distribution decisions (Jawahar, 2002) while procedural justice urges upon how the procedures determining the distribution of organizational resources are perceived (Folgerve Greenberg, 1985). Interactional justice is related to the opinion on the quality of interpersonal conduct (kindness, respect and integrity etc.) (BiesveMoag, 1986).

The innovation and changes developed by an organization to grow stronger against the resistance created by the competitive environment may increase its competitive power while any negative reactions to them may negatively affect this power. This may be, externally, an evidence of it continuing its existence, but, may internally, make employees experience difficulties in dealing with the changes. If the unity is damaged when internal powers continue to cooperate in order to achieve the goals of the organization, this may result in disbelief in the changes and innovations introduced by the organization and negative reactions against the organization. This may cause the concept of organizational cynicism. Organizational cynicism is defined as "one's negative attitude towards their employing organization" (Dean et al., 1998). In general, organizational cynicism is addressed in literature under three main categories cognitive cynicism, emotional cynicism and behavioural cynicism. The cognitive view to cynicism is grounded on the belief that the organization is lack of integrity (equality, honesty, sincerity etc.) (Dean et al., 1998) while emotional view to it emphasizes the negative emotions (such as anger, distress, weariness, aversion, hatred, arrogance, disrespectfulness, frustration, insecurity, shame, etc.) towards the organization (Abraham, 2000; Dean et al., 1998). And behavioural view covers the tendency to behave insulting and critical towards the organization (Dean et al., 1998).

The main factors determining the organizations' objectives and levels of success are formed by psychological, namely emotional, factors such as justice, trust, satisfaction, motivation, loyalty (Koç and Yazıcıoğlu, 2011). This study addresses the

organizational justice and organizational cynicism among these factors affecting the organizational behaviour.

When studies on organizational justice and organizational cynicism in Turkey are examined, it is seen most of the studies have been performed on the level of corporations (Çağ, 2011; Çalışkan, 2014; Efeoğlu and İplik, 2011; Kurtanis and Çetinel, 2010; Özler, Atalay and Şahin, 2010; Sancak, 2014; Tokgöz, 2011; Türköz, Polat and Coşar, 2013), and that studies at educational organizations are quite limited in number (Bölükbaşıoğlu, 2013; Çetin, Özgan&Bozbayındır, 2013; Köybaşı, Uğurlu&Öncel, 2017). Based on the former studies it can be put forth that perceived organizational justice and organizational cynicism reflects on teachers' performance at educational institutions. Considering how vital educational institutions are for a country's future, it is anticipated that any prospective study, including this one, shall contribute to the national educational system.

This study aims to investigate what is the level of the organizational justice and organizational cynicism as perceived by teachers and if there is a correlation between their perceived organizational justice and perceived cynicism. Answers were sought for the following questions through the study designed using survey model:

1. What is the level of the organizational justice as perceived by vocational high school teachers?
2. What is the level of the organizational cynicism as perceived by vocational high school teachers?
3. Is there any correlation between the organizational justice and cynicism as perceived by vocational high school teachers?

2. Material and Methods

In this chapter of the study; research model, study group, data collection techniques and data analysis are presented.

2.1 Research Model

In this study, descriptive relational screening model will be used. Screening models are research approaches that intend to describe any past or existing condition as is (Karasar, 2014).

2.2 Study Group

Population of the study is composed of 286 teachers that work at vocational and technical Anatolian high schools in Bağcılar district in the province of Istanbul in the academic years of 2016-2017.

2.3 Data Collection Techniques

Vocational high school teachers' perceived justice on their school is measured by "Scale of Organizational Justice Scale", which was designed by Niehoff and Moorman (1993), and translated to Turkish by Polat (2007) after which validity and reliability studies

were performed. As a result of reliability analysis by the researcher, reliability Cronbach Alpha coefficient was found to be .94 for entirety of the scale. Reliability coefficients for sub dimensions of the organizational justice are calculated to be .84, procedural justice to be .92, and interactional justice to be .87. Organizational justice scale is composed of three dimensions in order to measure perceived distributive justice, perceived procedural justice, and perceived interactional justice. Distributive justice dimension contains 6 expressions while procedural justice contains 9 and interactional justice contains 5.

Vocational high school teachers' organizational cynicism on their school is measured by "Organizational Cynicism Scale", which was designed by Brandes, Dharwadkar and Dean (1999), and translated to Turkish Kalağan (2009) after which validity and reliability studies were performed. As a result of reliability analysis by the researcher, reliability Cronbach Alpha coefficient was found to be .92 for entirety of the scale. Reliability coefficients for sub dimensions of the organizational cynicism are calculated to be .85 for cognitive cynicism, .97 for affective cynicism and .82 for behavioral cynicism. Organizational cynicism scale is composed of three dimensions, namely, cognitive, affective and behavioral. Cognitive cynicism dimension contains 5 expressions while affective cynicism contains 4 and behavioral cynicism contains 4.

An Organizational Justice and Organizational Cynicism Scale has been designed as 5-Point Likert Scale. Articles on 5-point Likert scale have five-range measure, that is, "(1) Strongly disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Neutral, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly agree". Codes of responses to each article on the questionnaire go from negative to positive, ranging between 1.00 and 5.00 in line with the scales. Assuming that ranges on the measurement tool are equal (4/5), lower and upper limits have been designated for the options initially. When interpreting arithmetic means, ranges have been evaluated as follows: 1.00-1.80 corresponds to "very low", 1.81-2.60 corresponds to "low", 2.61-3.40 corresponds to "moderate", corresponds to 3.41-4.20 "high", and 4.21-5.00 corresponds to "very high".

2.4 Data Analysis

In analyzing and evaluating research findings, SPSS statistical packaged software has been used, and arithmetic mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation analysis have been made based on the data.

3. Findings

Findings of data relating to the study have been provided in this chapter.

3.1 Findings for the First Question

Descriptive statistics relating to organizational justice perceived by teachers are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Results Relating to Organizational Justice Perceived by Vocational High School Teachers (n=286)

Dimensions of Organizational Justice	$\bar{X}$	ss	Level
Distributive justice	3.23	0.88	Moderate
Procedural justice	3.16	0.82	Moderate
Affective justice	3.66	0.84	High
Perceived Organizational Justice (General)	3.35	0.75	Moderate

On examining Table 1, it is seen that organizational justice perceived by teachers is on moderate level of $\bar{X}=3.23$ for distributive justice dimension, on moderate level of $\bar{X}=3.16$ for procedural justice dimension, on high level of $\bar{X}=3.66$ for interactional justice dimension, and eventually is on moderate level of $\bar{X}=3.35$ arithmetic mean on total dimension for organizational justice in general. It is further seen that organizational justice perceived by teachers is the highest on interactional justice dimension.

3.2 Findings and Interpretations for Second Sub Problem

Descriptive statistics relating to organizational cynicism perceived by teachers are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Results Relating to Levels of Organizational Cynicism Perceived by Teachers (N=286)

Dimension	$\bar{X}$	ss	Level
Cognitive cynicism	2.97	0.86	Moderate
Affective cynicism	2.20	1.19	Low
Behavioral cynicism	3.10	0.97	Moderate
Perceived Organizational Cynicism (General)	2.76	0.86	Moderate

On examining Table 2, it is seen that organizational cynicism perceived by teachers is on moderate level of $\bar{X}=2.97$ arithmetic mean for cognitive cynicism dimension, on moderate-low level of $\bar{X}=2.20$ arithmetic mean for affective cynicism dimension, on moderate level of $\bar{X}=3.10$ arithmetic mean for behavioral cynicism dimension, and eventually is on moderate level of $\bar{X}=2.76$ arithmetic mean on total dimension for organizational cynicism in general. It is further seen that organizational cynicism perceived by teachers is the highest on behavioral cynicism with $\bar{X}=3.10$ dimension and is the lowest on affective cynicism with $\bar{X}=2.20$ dimension.

3.3 Findings and Interpretations for Third Sub Problem

Correlation between perceived organizational justice and perceived organizational cynicism has been calculated by using "Pearson coefficient of correlation". Absolute value of correlation coefficient as "0.00-0.10" means no correlation exists while 0.10-0.30 refers to a "weak" correlation, 0.30- 0.50 refers to a "moderate" correlation, 0.50-0.70 refers to a "strong" correlation, and 0.70-1.00 refers to a "very strong" correlation (Jawlik, 2016). Results of the study are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation Test for Correlation between Organizational Justice and Organizational cynicism Perceived by Teachers (N=286)

Scale	Organizational Cynicism Scale					
	Cognitive cynicism	Affective cynicism	Behavioral cynicism	Perceived Organizational cynicism		
Organizational Justice Scale	Distributive justice	r	-.617***	-.582***	-.446***	-.641**
		p	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Procedural justice	r	-.533***	-.437***	-.423***	-.538**
		p	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Interactional justice	r	-.533***	-.416***	-.293***	-.480**
		p	0.000	0.000	0.000	0,000
	Perceived organizational justice	r	-.641**	-.547**	-.442**	-.632**
		p	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

*** p<.001

On examining Table 3, it is observed that a meaningful correlation that is negative and of p<.001 level exists between all dimensions of organizational justice and organizational cynicism perceived by teachers. Accordingly;

There is a strongly negative correlation between perceived distributive justice and cognitive cynicism (r=-.617 and p<.001), and affective cynicism (r =-.582 and p<.001) and perceived organizational cynicism in general (r =-.641 and p<.001), while the correlation with perceived behavioral cynicism (r =-.446 and p<.001) is moderately negative. The higher perceived distributive justice is the lower perceived organizational cynicism is.

There is a strongly negative correlation between perceived procedural justice and perceived cognitive cynicism (r =-.533 and p<.001) and perceived organizational cynicism in general (r =-.538 and p<.001), while the correlation between perceived affective cynicism (r =-.437 and p<.001) and perceived behavioral cynicism (r =-.423 and p<.001) is moderately negative. The higher perceived procedural justice is the lower perceived organizational cynicism is.

There is a strongly negative correlation between perceived interactional justice and perceived cognitive cynicism (r =-.533 and p<.001) while the correlation between perceived affective cynicism (r =-.416 and p<.001) and perceived organizational cynicism in general (r =-.480 and p<.001) is moderately negative, and it is poorly negative with perceived behavioral cynicism (r =-.293 and p<.001). The higher perceived interactional justice is the lower perceived organizational cynicism is.

Finally, a strongly negative correlation exists between perceived organizational justice in general and cognitive cynicism (r =-.641 and p<.001), affective cynicism (r =-.547 and p<.001), and perceived organizational cynicism in general (r =-.632 and p<.001) while the correlation between perceived organizational justice and behavioral cynicism (r =-.442 and p<.001) is moderately negative. The higher perceived organizational justice is the lower perceived organizational cynicism is.

4. Results and Discussion

Employees are quite sensitive that decision making process is consistent, unbiased, and careful and that it responds to their needs, wants and expectations. The way executives treat them and communicate with them in a decision making process are also important. It is a fact that perceived organizational justice is affected by the norms and values adopted by organizations, as well as the way outputs are distributed and the way employees are treated by their employers. Organizations that respond to these expectations are recognized as fair and just while those that violate them are recognized as unfair and unjust. The latter arouses negative feelings against the organization, which, in turn, paves the ground for organizational cynicism that is seen as one of the safe means for directly rising against organizational injustice.

It is demonstrated in this study that organizational justice perceived by vocational high school teachers is on a moderate level for distributive, procedural and total dimensions or perceived organizational justice, and is on high level for interactional justice dimension. When examining this study in terms of interactional justice, it can be said that school administrations are particular on communication with teachers, and show respect. When average points for dimensions and overall scale are evaluated in combination, it can be said that organizational justice perceived by teachers at school is on a moderate level. On examining studies in this particular matter, Demircan (2003), Dilek (2005), Karabay (2004), Sezen, (2001), Tan (2006) show in their studies that perceived organizational justice is on moderate level. Teachers tend to react to decisions made by the organization when they perceive distributive injustice, but they can react to entirety of the organization when they perceive procedural injustice. When they perceive interactional injustice, they can react to their superiors in person. Results of any such reactions can be harmful for schools, consequently for society at large. Specifying that organizational justice perceived by teachers in on moderate level, this study demonstrates that there is risk of decrease in the level organizational justice at educational institutions.

In this study, it is seen that organizational cynicism perceived by vocational high school teachers are on moderate level for cognitive, behavioral and total organizational cynicism in general, and are on low level for affective cynicism dimension. Behavioral, cognitive and cynicism in general perceived by vocational high school teachers is on "moderate" level while perceived affective cynicism is on "low" level. On examining it in terms of perceived affective cynicism, it can be said that subject teachers do not have negative feelings for the educational institution, and their values match with those of the institution they work for. On evaluation the results in general, it is observed that cynicism perceived by the vocational high school teachers that have taken part in this study is on moderate level. On examining the relevant studies Arslan (2012), Erdost et al., (2007), Özgan, Külekçi and Özkan (2012), Tokgöz and Yılmaz (2008), Tükeltürk et al., (2009), Yetim and Ceylan (2011) and Yüksel (2015) demonstrate that perceived organizational cynicism is on moderate level. Revealing itself when organizational expectations are not met at schools, organizational cynicism result in mental and neural

disorders such as disappointment, reluctance, despair, emotional burnout, depression in addition to psychological conditions such as rage, suspicion, tension, anger, discomposure, and defensive behaviors. Specifying that organizational cynicism perceived by vocational high school teachers is on a moderate level, this study demonstrates that there is a risk of decrease in the level of organizational cynicism at educational institutions.

It has been found that a negative and strongly meaningful correlation exists between organizational justice and organizational cynicism as perceived by the vocational high school teachers. Anderson (1996), Bernerth et al., (2007), Bölükbaşıoğlu (2013), Çetin, Özgan and Bozbayındır (2013), Efeoğlu and İplik (2011), Fitzgerald (2002), James (2005), Kutanis and Çetinel (2009), Köybaşı, Uğurlu and Öncel (2017), Lind and Tyler (1988), Tokgöz (2011) demonstrate in their studies that a negative correlation exists between perceived organizational justice and perceived organizational cynicism. It can be concluded that perceived organizational justice is high wherever organizational acquisitions are distributed fairly amongst teachers, the process of distributing these acquisitions is consistent and interactions by and between the educational personnel are positive; and that teachers' negative attitudes on cognitive, affective and behavioral dimensions (perceived cynicism) decrease whenever perceived organizational justice is improved.

5. Conclusion

This study scrutinizes the level of perceived organizational justice and perceived organizational cynicism for vocational high school teachers and whether a correlation exists between perceived organizational justice and perceived organizational cynicism. As it appears from the study, perceived organizational justice and organizational cynicism in general is on a "moderate" level for vocational high school teachers. A negative "high" level of meaningful correlation is found to exist between perceived organizational justice and organizational cynicism. The higher the perceived organizational justice is, the less the perceived organizational cynicism is.

6. Suggestions

Recommendations based on the results of this study can be itemized as follows:

- Perceived organizational justice is on a moderate level for teachers. To improve perceived organizational justice, school administrations and teachers can be supported with on-the-job training on organizational justice.
- Operation, procedures, goals and strategies, values, school mission and vision can be introduced and clarified to teachers by the school administration so that teachers are familiar with how a decision is made, in what possible ways applications and practices would affect them, how they can have access to information on decisions made or applications followed, and what could be done in case of injustice.

- School administration may invite teachers to take part in the decisions made, and share responsibilities and leadership. School administration can be rewarded materially and spiritually when they act in line with ethical values such as integrity, honesty and equality that positively affect perceived organizational justice, and contribute to improve a democratic environment at school.
- School administration may place emphasis that rewards are fit for motivating teachers both materially and spiritually.
- Perceived organizational cynicism is on a moderate level for teachers. To minimize perceived organizational cynicism, measures that help reduce organizational cynicism can be taken. Examples for measures are doing no wrong, acting in a way to safeguard justice, safety and social support, improving sense of belonging, reducing work load, preventing lack of inter organizational communication.
- Teachers can be appreciated and they can be consulted for their opinions and their opinion can be put into practice.
- School administration and teachers can be supported with on-the-job training to encourage them for innovations and change.
- At in-school activities, teachers can be given space to unlock and reveal their capabilities.

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